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Evolution of Internet Access in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in V4 Countries as a Driver of Digital Transformation (2017–2022)*Sylwia Kruk*^a

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Abstract

The aim of this article is to analyse the use of the Internet and selected digital technologies in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the Visegrad Group (V4) countries over the period 2017–2022. The study covers indicators related to employees' access to the Internet, the use of DSL and other fixed broadband connections, as well as the provision of mobile devices enabling Internet access for business purposes. The analyses were based on Eurostat data and include comparisons with average values for the EU-27.

The results show that most small and medium-sized enterprises in the V4 countries provide their employees with access to the Internet, although a consistent increase in this share was observed only in Poland, while the lowest levels were recorded in Hungary. In all analysed countries, the share of employees with Internet access for business purposes also increased, yet it remained below the EU-27 average. With regard to the use of broadband connections, the largest decline was noted in Czechia, while slight increases were observed in Poland and Slovakia. Over the analysed period, the proportion of enterprises equipping employees with mobile devices enabling Internet access for business purposes rose systematically, with Czechia consistently achieving values well above the EU-27 average.

Overall, the findings confirm a growing level of Internet access and the uptake of mobile technologies among small and medium-sized enterprises in the Visegrad Group, although these levels generally remained below the EU-27 average. The added value of the study lies in offering a new comparative perspective on SMEs in the Visegrad countries across five key

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indicators for the period 2017–2022, as well as in identifying divergent digitalisation trajectories within the group.

Keywords: digital transformation; small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs); Visegrad Group (V4); Internet access; broadband technologies; mobile technologies

1. Introduction

Digital transformation is associated with the introduction of digital solutions based on modern digital solutions. They provide enterprises with the opportunity to transform their business models, customer service standards and to introduce new products and services. Digital technologies foster the improvement of processes in enterprises and thus improve the efficiency of operations. However, the use of the Internet in SMEs depends on the access to the Internet. The use of new technologies in the SME sector creates the right conditions for them to grow in domestic and foreign markets, hence the use of the Internet can be one of the ways to increase competitiveness of enterprises.

The Internet has an impact on pricing and procurement policy in enterprises, as it enables information on potential business partners and their proposed prices to be obtained quickly and cheaply. When concluding transactions, physical distance is no longer an important factor, as it removes the need for personal contact with the seller (service provider). Reaching the target group does not require the involvement of intermediaries, which translates into reduced costs. An important role here is played by the use of social media, including the regular publication of content, which builds trust and loyalty to the enterprise. In the context of marketing and sales, it also makes it possible to place orders efficiently and improve their coordination, so that the number of accepted orders can be higher, and it also makes it easier to promote products and services, collect and sort information about customers and changes in the company's environment.

The use of the Internet improves communication and enables employees to be employed in remote working systems, which reduces the costs associated with creating and maintaining a permanent workplace.

Access to knowledge and improving the speed and efficiency of information flow within an enterprise have a positive impact on improving its efficiency. It should be noted that only

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enterprises with the right knowledge are in a position to fulfil the postulate of survival and development.

In view of the above, it should be noted that some enterprises choose not to use the Internet in their business. The reasons for this could be found in the underestimation of the impact of the Internet on business development and in material barriers, whereby the use of the Internet may appear as an unnecessary additional expense.

2. Methodology

The subject of the study was Internet access among small and medium-sized enterprises in the Visegrad Group countries. The research focused on SMEs as defined by Eurostat, namely¹:

- small enterprises employing between 10 and 49 persons,
- medium-sized enterprises employing between 50 and 249 persons.

From a spatial perspective, the analysis covered the Visegrad Group countries: Czechia, Hungary, Poland and Slovakia. The period 2017–2022 was selected as the most recent and consistently available timeframe within the Eurostat database.

Within this scope, the detailed analysis included indicators related to:

- percentage of enterprises where persons employed have access to the internet,
- percentage of employees who have access to the internet for business purposes,
- percentage of enterprises which use DSL or other broadband connection,
- percentage of enterprises which provide more than 20% of the employed persons with a portable device that allows internet connection via mobile telephone networks, for business purpose,
- percentage of employees which were provided a portable device that allows internet connection via mobile telephone networks, for business purpose.

In view of the above, the following research question was formulated: Did the changes observed in Internet access among small and medium-sized enterprises in the V4 countries follow a similar pattern, or did they differ across countries, and what are the implications of these patterns for future development opportunities?

¹ Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/isoc_e_esms.htm, [24.02.2026].

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Numerical data for the years 2017–2022 for the V4 countries, along with average values for the EU-27, are presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

3. Results and discussion

Internet access in enterprises

The analyses carried out allowed us to conclude that in the vast majority of small and medium-sized enterprises, employees have access to the Internet. At the same time, only in Poland this percentage increased in each of the periods analysed; the increase in this indicator in 2022 compared to 2017 was 3.7 p.p. Hungary showed the lowest performance in all analysed periods, deviating from the EU-27 average; at the same time, the percentage of enterprises where employees have access to the Internet fluctuated slightly there and increased (between 2017 and 2022) by 1.7 p.p., while the EU average increased by 1.9 p.p. during this period. In the Czech Republic and Slovakia, the percentage of enterprises with Internet access decreased in 2022 compared to 2017 by 1.5 p.p. and 0.3 p.p. respectively. In both these countries, 97.5% of enterprises had access to the Internet in 2017 and this result was higher than the EU-27 average representing 100.5% of its value. In 2022, this percentage was already only 97.1% and 98.3% of the EU-27 average respectively, which was slightly lower than the level recorded in Poland.

It is worth mentioning at this point that, at the same time, there was not much divergence in the values of this indicator for large scale enterprises in the countries in question during the analysed period. In the Czech Republic, Poland and Slovakia, the level of Internet access in enterprises employing at least 250 people exceeded 99.0% in 2017 and increased in subsequent periods to reach 99.8% in Hungary and Slovakia and 99.9% in the Czech Republic in 2022, while the EU-27 average was 99.9% in that period. At the same time, 100.0% of large scale enterprises in Poland in 2022 had Internet access and this level was 0.1 p.p. higher than the EU-27 average. In the V4 countries, there was no significant gap between large and small and medium-sized enterprises in terms of the value of this indicator. Between 2017 and 2022, the difference in the value of this indicator on average in the EU-27 between those two groups of enterprises narrowed from 2.7 p.p. to 1.0 p.p.

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Table 1. Internet access in SMEs in V4 countries in the years 2017-2022

Country	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Change 2022/2017 [values of part A] (in p.p.)
	A						B						
	Percentage (%)						The indicator's level in relation to EU-27 (%)						
Enterprises where persons employed have access to the internet (% of enterprises)													
Czechia	97.5	97.8	97.0	98.3	95.9	96.0	100.5	100.7	99.7	100.4	97.6	97.1	-1.5
Hungary	93.0	91.0	92.7	93.4	93.3	94.7	95.9	93.7	95.3	95.4	94.9	95.8	1.7
Poland	94.7	95.5	96.1	98.5	98.4	98.4	97.6	98.4	98.8	100.6	100.1	99.5	3.7
Slovakia	97.5	96.1	95.4	95.8	94.7	97.2	100.5	99.0	98.0	97.9	96.3	98.3	-0.3
EU-27	97.0	97.1	97.3	97.9	98.3	98.9	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	1.9
Persons employed have access to the internet for business purposes (% of total employment)													
Czechia	42.7	43.8	47.0	49.5	48.3	50.6	90.1	88.1	92.0	91.7	86.1	88.2	7.9
Hungary	39.1	39.6	39.3	41.7	48.6	52.0	82.5	79.7	76.9	77.2	86.6	90.6	12.9
Poland	37.8	38.7	40.8	48.3	50.6	50.6	79.7	77.9	79.8	89.4	90.2	88.2	12.8
Slovakia	43.8	43.1	44.6	50.2	51.2	53.9	92.4	86.7	87.3	93.0	91.3	93.9	10.1
EU-27	47.4	49.7	51.1	54.0	56.1	57.4	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	10.0

Source: own elaboration based on: Eurostat, Digital Economy and Society. Database, retrieved from: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/digital-economy-and-society/database> [14.12.2023].

Among the V4 countries, on the other hand, this difference showed an increasing trend in the Czech Republic (from 2.1 p.p. in 2017 to 3.9 p.p. in 2022) and Slovakia (from 1.7 p.p. in 2017 to 2.6 p.p. in 2022). In Hungary, it remained relatively stable (5.7 in 2017, 5.1 in 2022) and in all periods under consideration it was higher by approximately 3-4 p.p. than the EU-27 average difference. In Poland, on the other hand, it decreased from 5.0 p.p. in 2017 to 1.6 p.p. in 2022, while at the same time it was still, in the last of the analysed years, 0.6 p.p. higher than the difference recorded on average in the EU-27. In summary, although there were differences in the level of Internet access in both groups of enterprises in the V4 countries during the analysed period, they were not significant.

Employees' access to the Internet for business purposes

The use of the Internet in business operations makes it possible to rapidly improve the effectiveness and efficiency of business operations, but the degree and manner of its use may

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depend on the industry. With regard to small and medium-sized enterprises in the V4 countries, the level of the indicator illustrating the percentage of employees with access to the Internet for business purposes in all analysed periods was below the average value in the EU-27, while in general, it was increasing in the analysed countries. In Hungary, Poland and Slovakia, the growth rate of this indicator between 2017 and 2022 was higher than the growth rate of its average value in the EU-27, which was 10.0 p.p. The highest growth was recorded in Hungary and Poland (by 12.9 and 12.8 p.p. respectively). In contrast, the lowest growth was shown in the Czech Republic (7.9 p.p.).

In 2020, there was a significant increase in the percentage of employees with access to the Internet for business purposes in the Czech Republic, Poland and Slovakia, suggesting that this was a direct result of the lockdown associated with the Covid-19 pandemic. Hungary only caught up with the other countries in 2021. In comparison, with regard to large scale enterprises, the percentage of employees with Internet access for business purposes increased evenly throughout the period under consideration. A spike in this percentage related to the Covid-19 pandemic was not observed here, but nevertheless this percentage in all V4 countries and all analysed years was below the EU-27 average². It is worth noting the differences between SMEs and large scale enterprises in terms of employee access to the Internet for business purposes. In all analysed years between 2017 and 2022, the percentage of employees in large scale enterprises with access to the Internet for business purposes increased, but remained slightly lower than the EU-27 average (53.6% in 2017 and 63.2% in 2022). The differences in the value of this indicator for SMEs and large scale enterprises for the EU-27 as a whole decreased from 6.2 p.p. in 2017 to 5.8 p.p. in 2022. It is noteworthy that in Slovakia, the percentage of employees in large scale enterprises with access to the Internet for business purposes increased throughout the period under consideration, also in relation to SMEs - the difference in the value of this indicator in both groups of enterprises was 2.8 p.p. in 2017 and 3.4 p.p. in 2022. Similarly, in the Czech Republic, the difference in the value of this indicator in both groups of enterprises fluctuated between 2017 and 2020, to increase to a level of approximately 3 p.p. in 2021 and 2022. However, it did not exceed the difference in the average value of these

² Eurostat, Digital Economy and Society. Database - retrieved from: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/digital-economy-and-society/database> [1.03.2024].

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indicators in the EU-27. In Poland, on the other hand, the difference in the percentage recorded for large and small and medium-sized enterprises was 4.3 p.p. in 2017, but increased to 6.4 p.p. in 2022. An even greater increase in the indicated difference was observed in Hungary, where in 2017 there was no significant difference in the percentage of employees using Internet access for business purposes in both groups of enterprises (the difference was 0.4 p.p.). In contrast, an increase in this difference was observed in 2022 to 9.9 p.p.

Use of DSL and broadband Internet

Digital Subscriber Line (DSL) or other fixed broadband connections enable faster data transmission than, for example, with ISDN (Integrated Services Digital Network) or modems. Their use in enterprises therefore significantly improves communication and online working: it gives fast access to data, enables contact with counterparties from all over the world and provides the opportunity to participate in online training or conferences. Analysis of the available data, presented in Table 2, allows us to conclude that in the period under consideration, the percentage of enterprises using DSL and other fixed broadband connections in the group of small and medium-sized enterprises remained relatively stable in the EU-27, oscillating in the range of 90.8-94.0%. It should be noted, however, that of the V4 countries analysed, only in the Czech Republic the percentage of SMEs using DSL or other fixed broadband connections exceeded the EU-27 average, but this was the case up to and including 2020, while in 2021-2022 it was below the EU average. With regard to the other countries under consideration, in each of the analysed periods, the percentage of enterprises using broadband connections was slightly below the EU-27 average, but not below 78% (Hungary, 2019).

Overall, the percentage of SMEs which used DSL or other fixed broadband connections across the EU-27 increased by 1.7 p.p. in 2022 compared to 2017. Interestingly, this percentage decreased between 2017 and 2019, then started to gradually increase from 2020 onwards, which can be linked to the COVID-19 pandemic and the increasing demand for stable Internet access³. Among the V4 countries, the largest changes related to broadband access were observed throughout the period under consideration in the Czech Republic, where the percentage of

³ Across the EU-27, a slight decrease (-0.7 p.p.) in the use of DSL or other fixed broadband between 2017 and 2019 was observed in enterprises with more than 250 employees, but by 2022, this percentage increased by 1.1 p.p. to reach 99.1% in the last year analysed.

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enterprises using this type of connection decreased by as much as 8.6 p.p. between 2017 and 2022. In Hungary, it showed only a slight decrease, while it increased a little in Poland and Slovakia.

Table 2. Type of connections to the internet and use of mobile connections to the internet in SMEs in V4 countries in the years 2017-2022

Country	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Change 2022/2017 [values of part A] (in p.p.)
	A						B						
	Percentage of enterprises (%)						The indicator's level in relation to EU-27 (%)						
Enterprises using DSL or other fixed broadband connection													
Czechia	97.3	96.6	96.1	98.0	91.6	88.7	105.4	105.5	105.8	105.6	97.8	94.3	-8.6
Hungary	86.9	82.4	78.0	82.6	80.1	85.2	94.1	90.0	85.9	89.0	85.5	90.6	-1.7
Poland	82.8	86.6	85.3	84.9	85.2	83.7	89.7	94.5	93.4	91.5	90.9	89.0	0.9
Slovakia	87.5	88.3	84.9	86.6	86.5	89.0	94.8	96.4	93.5	93.3	92.3	94.7	1.5
EU-27	92.3	91.6	90.8	92.8	93.7	94.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	1.7
Enterprises providing more than 20% of the employed persons with a portable device that allows internet connection via mobile telephone networks, for business purpose													
Czechia	NA*	50.4	49.9	56.8	57.9	61.3	NA	149.1	138.2	146.8	138.2	127.2	10.9**
Hungary	NA	35.2	35.8	40.6	41.5	46.5	NA	104.1	99.2	104.9 ^s	99.0	96.5	11.3**
Poland	NA	31.9	36.0	42.7	45.5	52.2	NA	94.4	99.7	110.3	108.6	108.3	20.3**
Slovakia	NA	32.7	32.9	38.3	43.1	45.1	NA	96.7	91.1	99.0	102.9	93.6	12.4**
EU-27	NA	33.8	36.1	38.7	41.9	48.2	NA	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	14.4**

Explanation: * - data not available.

** - ze względu na brak danych, jako rok bazowy przyjęto 2018 rok.

Source: own elaboration based on: Eurostat, Digital Economy and Society. Database, retrieved from: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/digital-economy-and-society/database> [14.12.2023].

It should also be noted that differences were observed in the use of DSL or other fixed broadband connections between small and medium-sized enterprises and large scale enterprises in the V4 countries. The largest differences were observed in Poland and Hungary (average

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difference of approximately 14 p.p.), followed by Slovakia (average difference of 10.6 p.p.). The smallest average difference was observed for the Czech Republic (average of 4.9 p.p.).

Use of mobile devices

Analyses on mobile Internet use, due to the lack of complete data, covered the period between 2018 and 2022. In 2018, in the EU-27, 33.8% of SMEs provided more than 20% of the employed persons with a mobile device that allowed Internet connection via mobile telephone networks, for business purposes (Table 2). At the same time, the percentage of employed persons, who were provided with a mobile device that allowed Internet connection via mobile telephone networks, for business purposes was at 23.2% of the total employed persons in SMEs in 2018, increasing to 33.7% of the total employed persons in SMEs in 2022 (Table 3). No abrupt change was observed here that could be linked, for example, to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 3. Persons employed, which were provided a portable device that allows internet connection via mobile telephone networks, for business purpose in SMEs in V4 countries in the years 2017-2022 (percentage of total employment)

Country	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Change 2022/ 2018 [values of part A] (in p.p.)
	A						B						
	Percentage of total employment (%)						The indicator's level in relation to EU-27 (%)						
Czechia	NA*	28.6	28.5	33.1	33.7	37.5	NA	123.3	114.5	124.9	117.0	111.3	8.9**
Hungary	NA	22.7	23.6	26.2	31.6	34.5	NA	97.8	94.8	98.9	109.7	102.4	11.8**
Poland	NA	21.1	23.2	27.8	30.7	34.6	NA	90.9	93.2	104.9	106.6	102.7	13.5**
Slovakia	NA	20.6	19.9	22.6	24.4	27.2	NA	88.8	79.9	85.3	84.7	80.7	6.6**
EU-27	NA	23.2	24.9	26.5	28.8	33.7	NA	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	10.5**

Explanation: * - data not available.

** - ze względu na brak danych, jako rok bazowy przyjęto 2018 rok.

Source: own elaboration based on: Eurostat, Digital Economy and Society. Database, retrieved from: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/digital-economy-and-society/database> [14.12.2023].

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In the following years, the percentage of SMEs that equipped at least 20% of their employees with mobile devices increased steadily: in 2018, it reached 33.8%, and in 2022 it already reached 48.2% of enterprises. In Hungary, Poland and Slovakia, the percentage of enterprises providing more than 20% of their employees with mobile devices that allowed Internet access was at a level close to the EU-27 average, while for the Czech Republic this percentage was higher by 15.5 p.p. on average for the entire period under consideration compared to the EU average for this period (39.7%). Interestingly, with regard to the Czech Republic and Slovakia, the percentage of employees who were equipped with mobile devices and the percentage of enterprises providing at least 20% of their employees with mobile devices was higher in SMEs than in large scale enterprises (3.3 p.p. and 3.7 p.p. and 6.4 p.p. and 9.6 p.p. respectively on average in the analysed period between 2018 and 2022). By contrast, in Poland and Hungary, more large scale companies than SMEs provided mobile devices to at least 20% of their employees and the percentage of employees equipped with such devices was also higher. The exception was 2018 for Hungary, where both the percentage of employees equipped with mobile devices and the percentage of enterprises providing at least 20% of employees with mobile devices were lower in large than in small enterprises (by 1.8 p.p. and 4.7 p.p. respectively).

In summary, it should be noted that overall in the EU-27, the percentage of total employment in small and medium-sized enterprises in which employees had access to the Internet for business purposes increased. This increase was observable in all V4 countries, at the same time this percentage was below the EU average throughout the analysed period. Also observable was an increase in the percentage of enterprises providing more than 20% of their employees with mobile devices enabling Internet access for business purposes. In Hungary, Poland and Slovakia, this percentage was generally similar to the EU-27 average, while in the Czech Republic this percentage was higher than the EU-27 average throughout the period under consideration.

4. Conclusions

The conducted analyses indicate that the further development of small and medium-sized enterprises in the Visegrad Group countries will largely depend on their ability to make fuller and more effective use of digital technologies.

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Across all analysed countries, small and medium-sized enterprises exhibited very high levels of Internet access (above 91%). The most substantial positive changes during the examined period were observed in Poland, whereas Czechia consistently recorded the highest levels of Internet access. Hungary remained the most lagging country relative to the EU-27 average. Within the Visegrad Group, no significant differences were found between large enterprises and SMEs with respect to this indicator.

In terms of employees' access to the Internet for business purposes, SMEs in all examined countries remained below the EU-27 average. Nevertheless, an increase was recorded across all V4 countries, with the strongest growth observed in Hungary and Poland, and the weakest in Czechia. A noticeable increase in 2020 was recorded in Czechia, Poland and Slovakia, which may be linked to the COVID-19 pandemic. In Hungary, the pandemic-related effect appeared with a one-year delay, in 2021. In contrast, no comparable “pandemic jump” was observed among large enterprises. This limited employee-level access to the Internet—despite relatively strong enterprise-level connectivity—may in practice hinder the adoption and effective use of digital tools. In this context, policy measures aimed at expanding Internet access directly at the workplace would be desirable. Failure to address this gap may contribute to widening productivity differences between SMEs in the V4 region and firms operating in more digitally advanced markets.

The use of broadband connections among small and medium-sized enterprises in the V4 countries is widespread; however, a clear decline was observed in Czechia (a decrease of 8.6 p.p.). In Hungary, the decline was minor, although the levels recorded there were frequently the lowest within the SME group. In contrast, Poland and Slovakia experienced slight increases, yet the values of the analysed indicators remained below the EU-27 average throughout the entire period. In this context, it appears justified to develop programmes specifically targeted at SMEs, aimed at compensating for existing infrastructure and resource gaps. At the same time, it would be important to systematically monitor differences between large enterprises and SMEs in this area.

Among small and medium-sized enterprises in the Visegrad Group countries, the use of mobile devices is becoming increasingly widespread. Slovakia remains the most delayed in this respect. In Hungary and Poland, the observed changes were broadly comparable to the EU-27

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average. Czechia, however, stands out as a clear leader in mobile transformation within the group, which suggests that it may serve as a useful benchmark for mobility-related policy initiatives in the remaining V4 countries.

Differences in the use of broadband connections and mobile devices indicate that the pace of digitalisation will vary across individual countries. The strong adoption of mobile devices among employees in Czechia provides the potential for a faster transition to more flexible work models and for broader implementation of digital solutions.

Digital transformation among small and medium-sized enterprises in the Visegrad Group is progressing; however, observable gaps and cross-country differences may limit the full uptake of digital technologies and undermine competitiveness. The disparities identified between SMEs and large enterprises in some countries indicate that future development prospects will depend on levelling conditions within the sector. If the relatively weak results recorded by SMEs persist, the Visegrad region will be less able to compete with firms from EU-27 countries in areas such as the implementation of digital services and integration into the digital market.

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